

Problems of Teaching English in Iraq Context: Teaching Speaking in Focus

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 22, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: June 23, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching Speaking , Teachers , Problems</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8075734</p>	<p><i>Teaching English as a foreign language is a complex process influenced by cultural, social, political, emotional, mental dimensions, and mental dimensions (Freeman & Anderson, 2011). It is important to pay attention to the learners' specific and unique needs in a certain class at a specific time, and the reality that these demands fluctuate from moment to moment. Therefore, teachers should attempt to meet the students' learning needs. According to Saeed and Jafar (2015) "There are several concerns concerning English teaching in Iraq, the most of them are connected to the learners themselves, cultural and environmental issues, and the educational system" (p.1). The present study is an attempt to explain the problems of teaching English in Iraq context, especially teaching speaking. In addition, some researchers (such as Aliakbari & Jamalvandi(2010), Liu, (2010), Paraded, (2011) Khosravi et al, (2014) Fauzi, (2017) proposed some ways to improve learners' speaking achievement as shown in the present study.</i></p>

Introduction

English is taught as an international language in the educational system in many countries over the world. According to Freeman and Anderson (2011), teaching is very complex, influenced not only by cultural, social, political, emotional, and mental dimensions but also requiring their contingent orchestration in support of students' learning. When language teaching, in particular, is in focus, the complexity is even greater, by teachers' view of language teaching and learning (Adamson, 2004, as cited in Freeman & Anderson, 2011). It is also important to pay attention to the learners' specific and unique needs in a particular class at a particular time, and the fact that these needs change from moment to moment. Therefore, teachers should attempt to meet their students' learning needs (Freeman & Anderson, 2011).

Yet, experience is essential to learning because learning is a lifelong process. For learning to be effective, the learners' experiences and subsequent emotional responses must be enjoyable to them. So, it is essential for educators to always adopt steps that will encourage positive emotional responses in their pupils and improve their learning prospects.

The environment in which people are studying has an impact on their ability to learn. Because of the environments and circumstances that are encountered, experience is gained. In light of this reality, teachers must create a setting that enhances the learning scenario. It means that learning needs to take place in a happy, relaxed setting. Teachers must exhibit sympathetic adoration in order to achieve this, as well as encourage sentiments of achievement, achievement, and respect. This will all encourage the pupils to pay attention to the lesson. A environment like this is thought to be extremely beneficial for learning since it can promote authentic language use, where kids feel safe contributing their own ideas and are able to express themselves. (Dakhil , T.A, 2023).

people of different social classes, ages, nations, and professions show a tendency towards learning foreign languages. It is maybe the result of their communication needs through another language, their job requirement and so forth. However, reporting from their point of view, lots of obstacles prohibit them from achieving their goals. The first and the most serious one is the lack of time also there are a variety of other reasons that many people look for new and interesting ways of learning or teaching languages. Furthermore, from among other problems, is the learner's likely outlook about the cliché physical class environment, not liking the teacher, class atmosphere can be mentioned. Therefore, new technologies can compensate for troubleshooting these problems and is regarded as a good resolution. (Lateef Al-Aaydie A.A, 2023)

Problems of teaching English in Iraqi Context

Every language carries culture both culture and language are actually interwoven and closely bonded. Based on this inseparability of culture and language, learning or teaching a language is by necessity learning or teaching culture. According to Ulaywi and Khairi (2008) "Understanding a language involves not only knowledge of grammar, phonology, and lexis but also certain features and characteristics of the culture" (p.135). It's important to note that Iraqi culture is particularly sensitive to the issue of reputation, and as a consequence, most people don't want to be linked with corrupted people in any way. According to Obaid Hussein and

Ibrahim Elttayef (2017), Arab students and teachers in general and Iraqi students in particular, face a lot of problems due to their social and cultural backgrounds when they are studying English as a foreign language. In addition, Teaching English in Arab countries, notably Iraq, has a number of obstacles that prevent teachers from carrying out their responsibilities properly. In Iraq, primary school teachers are commonly observed dealing with a variety of issues. The teacher's inability to use modern EFL teaching practices, the absence of creative teaching strategies, the lack of technology resources, and the inadequacy of educational programs are all big roadblocks.

According to AL-Akraa (2013) "Despite their language skills, most teachers are not equipped to teach English to students of all ages and abilities. As a result, Iraqi instructors may struggle to develop lesson plans since they lack the skills and experience to apply various instructional styles with their pupils based on their age" (p.2). Iraqi English instructors are victims of the country's inadequate/corrupted educational system. Rashid (2016) The studies were educated and graduated without gaining adequate information or experience. The classroom surroundings do not encourage students to develop adequate professional judgment (p.18).

Teaching Speaking in English in the Iraqi context

According to Adhikari (2010) "Speaking is the most common mode of communication. Learning to speak English is sometimes linked with learning English as a whole" (p. 1). According to Abdulhussein and Mohammed (2015) "Speaking form and meaning are influenced by the context in which they occur, which includes the individuals themselves, their collective experiences, the physical surroundings, and the reason for speaking". There are a variety of reasons that contribute to EFL students' difficulty speaking English. Some of these variables have to do with the students themselves, the curriculum, and the surrounding environment. Both speaking and writing are difficult for Arab English learners. Learners' weaknesses might stem from a lack of exposure to the target language environment as well as a lack of desire on the part of the students.

According to Hussein and Albakri (2019) "Many Arab learners are taught English in their primary and secondary schools, but they are taught English only as a formality" (p.54). Iraqi students suffer when it comes to speaking English as a foreign language at school. The main root of the problem is that English classes in Iraq are unsuccessful in strengthening students' English-speaking ability. Due to challenges in expressing oneself in English, a significant proportion of students do not engage in class discussions. Kareem (2020) "One of the biggest challenges that teachers may face is the insufficient knowledge of the students' needs and the lack of knowledge of vocabulary reasons for the difficulty of speaking English as a foreign language" (p.5).

Improving learners' speaking ability

According to Fauzi (2017) small group dissection can be effective in improving learners' speaking ability. Through discussion, learners can interact with each other as well as motivate and encourage to use the target language. The effect of reading short stories on EFL students' speaking and listening abilities. The results of the study demonstrated that reading short stories can help the experimental group enhance their speaking and listening skills. The findings of this study may assist learners to improve their independent English language learning and speech abilities by reading short stories. According to Khosravi et al. (2014), the approach of reading condensed short tales helps improve learners' speaking skills. The findings show that exposure to appropriate literary texts had a substantial impact on EFL learners' listening abilities. In line with the study, Paraded (2011) telling the story can improve learners' speaking ability. He felt that by doing a chain exercise of recounting a narrative in small groups, each student would have several opportunities to practice the meaningful context. Aliakbari and Jamalvandi (2010) emphasize the impacts of 'Role Play' as a TBLT-centered activity were explored, as well as whether it may increase EFL learners' oral skills. The results showed that the TBLT-based role-play strategy improved EFL learners' speaking competence. They concluded that this practice can help students enhance their speech abilities. For oral English lessons, spoken English tests and role-play exercises were regarded to be two forms of English teaching activities. Role-playing is more effective than oral English exams in raising college students' enthusiasm to speak English, according to the study premise. According to Liu (2010), students in the Target Group who participate in role-playing activities become more engaged in speaking English than students in the Control Group who take oral English assessments. This study discovered that role-playing increased students' enthusiasm to speak English.

Conclusion

Many factors are suggested to play a role in EFL students' difficulties speaking English. Furthermore, Arab English learners struggle with both speaking and writing. Learners' weaknesses can be attributed to a lack of exposure to the target language environment as well as a lack of motivation on their part. While speaking English as a foreign language, Iraqi students face difficulties in school. The main cause of the difficulty in speaking is because English programs in Iraq are ineffective in strengthening students' English-speaking ability. Due to difficulties in expressing themselves, a significant number of students do not participate in class discussions. Some methods to increase learners' speaking abilities were previously described. It is considered that these methods may help learners enhance their speaking skills in Iraq.

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